

Table 1. Defining points for IFOV profiles

90 μm		100 μm		110 μm	
ρ	$\Psi(\rho)$	ρ	$\Psi(\rho)$	ρ	$\Psi(\rho)$
10.7 as	1.00	12.00	1.000	13.33	1.000
11.4	.97	12.33	.996	13.67	.996
12.2	.89	12.67	.986	14.00	.986
13.0	.76	13.00	.969	14.33	.969
13.8	.58	13.33	.944	14.67	.944
14.7	.39	13.67	.909	15.00	.910
15.5	.23	14.00	.866	15.33	.867
16.3	.10	14.33	.814	15.67	.815
17.2	.03	14.67	.754	16.00	.756
18.8	.00	15.00	.687	16.33	.689
		15.33	.615	16.67	.617
		15.67	.540	17.00	.542
		16.00	.464	17.33	.466
		16.33	.389	17.67	.391
		16.67	.317	18.00	.319
		17.00	.251	18.33	.252
		17.33	.192	18.67	.193
		17.67	.140	19.00	.140
		18.00	.096	19.33	.096
		18.33	.061	19.67	.061
		18.67	.035	20.00	.036
		19.00	.017	20.33	.017
		19.33	.006	20.67	.006
		19.67	.000	21.00	.000

AVERAGE IDT SIGNAL PARAMETERS VS. RADIAL IFOV OFFSET

3(11)

RUN# 11 TEL.DEFOC=15 RO.DEFOC=0 IFOV=90 Z0=0.0" T0=.989

R [ASJ]	EO(R) +/-	M1(R) +/-	M2(R) +/-	RMS-D1(R) [MASJ]	RMS-D2(R) [MASJ]
.0	.992 .000	.811 .000	.341 .000	.0	.0
.5	.998 .002	.815 .001	.343 .000	.2	.1
1.0	.999 .000	.815 .000	.343 .000	.1	.0
1.5	.999 .001	.815 .001	.343 .000	.0	.0
2.0	.999-.001	.815 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
2.5	.999 .000	.815 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
3.0	.999-.001	.815-.001	.343 .000	.0	.0
3.5	.999-.001	.815 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
4.0	.998-.001	.815-.001	.343 .000	.0	.0
4.5	.998 .001	.815-.001	.343 .000	.0	.0
5.0	.998-.001	.815 .001	.343 .000	.0	.0
5.5	.998 .001	.816 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
6.0	.997-.001	.816 .001	.343 .000	.0	.0
6.5	.997-.001	.816 .001	.343 .000	.0	.0
7.0	.996 .001	.816-.001	.343 .000	.0	.0
7.5	.995-.001	.816 .000	.344 .000	.0	.0
8.0	.995 .001	.817 .001	.344 .000	.0	.0
8.5	.994 .001	.817 .001	.344 .000	.0	.0
9.0	.992 .001	.818 .001	.344 .000	.1	.0
9.5	.990 .001	.818 .000	.345 .000	.1	.0
10.0	.988 .002	.819 .000	.345 .001	.1	.0
10.5	.983 .003	.822 .002	.346 .001	.4	.1
11.0	.970 .009	.826 .002	.348 .001	1.0	.1
11.5	.939 .019	.827 .003	.348 .002	1.8	.2
12.0	.888 .023	.827 .005	.348 .003	2.8	.3
12.5	.821 .029	.828 .007	.348 .004	3.7	.3
13.0	.737 .039	.828 .010	.348 .006	5.3	.6
13.5	.639 .043	.823 .012	.346 .007	6.9	.9
14.0	.532 .039	.817 .014	.343 .009	8.1	.8
14.5	.431 .040	.816 .017	.342 .010	10.0	1.0
15.0	.336 .044	.808 .022	.338 .013	12.4	1.5
15.5	.240 .034	.787 .026	.328 .016	16.5	2.0
16.0	.161 .027	.756 .029	.314 .018	19.4	2.1
16.5	.101 .020	.719 .033	.295 .020	23.6	2.5
17.0	.063 .014	.661 .035	.267 .022	26.8	2.9
17.5	.038 .007	.612 .028	.236 .019	27.0	3.1
18.0	.025 .004	.572 .042	.208 .024	26.5	4.8
18.5	.016 .003	.485 .053	.159 .032	31.2	7.6
19.0	.011 .002	.422 .042	.114 .030	33.2	13.2
19.5	.009 .001	.410 .042	.104 .032	30.3	17.2
20.0	.008 .001	.422 .046	.098 .029	26.7	15.9
20.5	.007 .001	.415 .047	.096 .030	24.7	15.5
21.0	.007 .001	.421 .047	.093 .029	22.7	14.2
21.5	.006 .001	.415 .053	.092 .028	20.4	13.4
22.0	.006 .001	.421 .053	.092 .027	18.2	12.2

AVERAGE IDT SIGNAL PARAMETERS VS. RADIAL IFOV OFFSET

4(11)

RUN# 12 TEL.DEFOC=15 RO.DEFOC=0 IFOV=100 ZO=0.0" TO=.991

R [CAS]	EO(R) +/-	M1(R) +/-	M2(R) +/-	RMS-D1(R) [MAS]	RMS-D2(R) [MAS]
.0	.992 .000	.810 .000	.341 .000	.0	.0
.5	.998 .002	.814 .001	.342 .000	.2	.1
1.0	.999 .001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.1	.0
1.5	.999 .000	.814 .001	.342 .000	.0	.0
2.0	.999 .000	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
2.5	.999 .000	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
3.0	.999-.001	.814 .001	.342 .000	.0	.0
3.5	.999-.001	.814-.001	.342 .000	.0	.0
4.0	.999-.001	.814-.001	.342 .000	.0	.0
4.5	.999 .000	.814-.001	.342 .000	.0	.0
5.0	.998-.001	.815 .001	.343 .000	.0	.0
5.5	.998 .000	.815-.001	.343 .000	.0	.0
6.0	.998-.001	.815-.001	.343 .000	.0	.0
6.5	.998-.001	.815 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
7.0	.997-.001	.815 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
7.5	.997 .002	.815 .001	.343 .000	.0	.0
8.0	.997 .000	.815 .001	.343 .000	.0	.0
8.5	.996 .001	.816 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
9.0	.995 .000	.816 .001	.343 .000	.0	.0
9.5	.994-.001	.816 .001	.343 .000	.0	.0
10.0	.994-.001	.817 .000	.344 .000	.1	.0
10.5	.992 .001	.817 .001	.344-.001	.1	.0
11.0	.990 .000	.818 .000	.344 .000	.1	.0
11.5	.988 .002	.819 .001	.345 .000	.2	.0
12.0	.983 .003	.821 .001	.346 .001	.4	.0
12.5	.969 .008	.824 .002	.347 .001	.8	.1
13.0	.943 .015	.826 .003	.347 .002	1.5	.1
13.5	.902 .021	.827 .004	.348 .003	2.4	.2
14.0	.841 .026	.827 .006	.348 .004	3.4	.4
14.5	.762 .034	.826 .008	.348 .005	4.7	.5
15.0	.673 .043	.824 .011	.347 .007	6.0	.7
15.5	.572 .040	.821 .013	.345 .008	7.9	.9
16.0	.464 .041	.815 .017	.342 .010	9.5	1.1
16.5	.359 .041	.805 .020	.337 .012	12.1	1.4
17.0	.267 .037	.791 .024	.330 .015	14.4	1.6
17.5	.185 .028	.770 .027	.320 .017	18.2	2.1
18.0	.118 .023	.731 .034	.301 .020	22.9	2.6
18.5	.071 .017	.668 .045	.269 .025	28.7	3.1
19.0	.040 .010	.575 .052	.217 .031	38.0	4.6
19.5	.022 .005	.439 .055	.147 .033	43.1	8.1
20.0	.015 .002	.401 .044	.108 .031	36.4	15.1
20.5	.012 .001	.423 .047	.109 .033	25.7	13.7
21.0	.011 .001	.424 .040	.101 .031	23.8	13.1
21.5	.010 .001	.422 .041	.100 .029	21.2	12.2
22.0	.009 .001	.423 .037	.096 .029	19.2	11.8

AVERAGE IDT SIGNAL PARAMETERS VS. RADIAL IFOV OFFSET

RUN# 13 TEL.DEFOC=15 RO.DEFOC=0 IFOV=110 Z0=0.0" T0=.992

R CASJ	ED(R) +/-	M1(R) +/-	M2(R) +/-	RMS-D1(R) [MASJ]	RMS-D2(R) [MASJ]
.0	.992 .000	.809 .000	.341 .000	.0	.0
.5	.998 .002	.814 .001	.342 .000	.2	.1
1.0	.999 .000	.814 .000	.342 .000	.1	.0
1.5	.999 .001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
2.0	.999 .001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
2.5	.999 .000	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
3.0	.999 .001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
3.5	.999 .001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
4.0	.999-.001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
4.5	.999-.001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
5.0	.999-.001	.814 .001	.342 .000	.0	.0
5.5	.998 .000	.814 .001	.342 .000	.0	.0
6.0	.998 .000	.814-.001	.342 .000	.0	.0
6.5	.998 .000	.814-.001	.342 .000	.0	.0
7.0	.998-.001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
7.5	.998-.002	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
8.0	.997 .001	.815 .001	.342 .000	.0	.0
8.5	.997 .000	.815 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
9.0	.997 .000	.815 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
9.5	.996 .001	.815-.001	.343 .000	.0	.0
10.0	.995 .001	.815-.001	.343 .000	.0	.0
10.5	.995 .000	.816 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
11.0	.994 .000	.816-.001	.343 .000	.1	.0
11.5	.993 .001	.816-.001	.343 .000	.1	.0
12.0	.991 .001	.817-.001	.344 .000	.1	.0
12.5	.989 .000	.818 .000	.344 .000	.1	.0
13.0	.986 .002	.819-.001	.345 .000	.2	.0
13.5	.979 .005	.822 .001	.346 .001	.5	.0
14.0	.963 .009	.824 .002	.347 .001	1.0	.1
14.5	.931 .016	.825 .003	.347 .002	1.8	.2
15.0	.885 .025	.826 .005	.348 .003	2.6	.3
15.5	.820 .029	.826 .006	.347 .004	3.8	.4
16.0	.736 .035	.825 .009	.347 .006	5.0	.6
16.5	.639 .041	.823 .012	.345 .007	6.7	.8
17.0	.539 .044	.818 .015	.343 .009	8.2	.9
17.5	.432 .040	.811 .018	.340 .011	10.4	1.2
18.0	.328 .038	.799 .021	.334 .013	12.7	1.4
18.5	.240 .036	.783 .026	.326 .015	15.3	1.7
19.0	.164 .027	.758 .028	.313 .018	19.9	2.3
19.5	.103 .020	.709 .036	.290 .021	23.9	2.6
20.0	.060 .014	.636 .047	.250 .026	31.4	3.4
20.5	.035 .009	.523 .061	.190 .033	38.1	5.0
21.0	.021 .004	.418 .041	.124 .032	39.2	9.7
21.5	.016 .002	.414 .043	.109 .031	27.3	12.6
22.0	.014 .002	.428 .037	.106 .032	20.7	10.7

AVERAGE IDT SIGNAL PARAMETERS VS. RADIAL IFOV OFFSET

6(11)

RUN# 14 TEL.DEFOC=15 RO.DEFOC=100 IFOV=90 Z0=3.5" T0=.986

R CASJ	ED(R) +/-	M1(R) +/-	M2(R) +/-	RMS-D1(R) [MASJ]	RMS-D2(R) [MASJ]
.0	1.000 .000	.815 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
.5	1.000 .000	.815 .001	.343 .000	.0	.0
1.0	1.000 .000	.815-.001	.343 .000	.1	.0
1.5	1.000 .001	.815 .001	.343 .000	.1	.0
2.0	.999 .000	.815 .000	.343 .000	.1	.0
2.5	.999-.001	.815 .001	.343 .000	.2	.0
3.0	.999-.001	.816 .000	.344 .000	.2	.0
3.5	.998 .001	.816-.001	.344 .000	.3	.0
4.0	.997 .001	.816 .001	.344 .000	.4	.0
4.5	.996 .001	.817 .001	.344 .000	.6	.0
5.0	.993 .003	.817 .002	.345 .001	.9	.1
5.5	.991 .004	.818 .002	.345 .001	1.1	.1
6.0	.987 .006	.819 .002	.345 .001	1.4	.2
6.5	.980 .009	.821 .003	.346 .001	2.1	.4
7.0	.974 .012	.823 .005	.347 .001	2.6	.5
7.5	.961 .017	.827 .006	.348 .002	3.6	.8
8.0	.951 .021	.829 .008	.350 .002	4.2	.9
8.5	.931 .025	.834 .010	.352 .003	5.6	1.2
9.0	.911 .029	.838 .012	.354 .005	6.9	1.5
9.5	.885 .033	.842 .016	.356 .007	8.6	1.8
10.0	.857 .036	.846 .019	.358 .010	10.5	2.2
10.5	.825 .035	.849 .026	.361 .014	12.1	2.6
11.0	.781 .033	.852 .032	.363 .018	15.0	3.3
11.5	.743 .036	.853 .041	.365 .024	17.0	3.8
12.0	.694 .033	.853 .049	.366 .030	20.2	4.7
12.5	.644 .032	.851 .063	.365 .038	22.8	5.4
13.0	.592 .036	.847 .075	.364 .045	26.1	6.3
13.5	.540 .038	.842 .087	.360 .052	29.3	7.3
14.0	.485 .041	.833 .103	.356 .061	32.6	8.3
14.5	.432 .047	.822 .114	.348 .067	36.7	9.5
15.0	.378 .051	.808 .134	.341 .077	39.1	10.2
15.5	.332 .052	.794 .141	.331 .079	43.8	11.5
16.0	.280 .056	.772 .162	.321 .088	46.5	12.2
16.5	.239 .057	.754 .169	.308 .089	51.3	13.4
17.0	.197 .055	.730 .184	.296 .094	54.0	14.2
17.5	.163 .052	.708 .189	.281 .093	58.4	15.4
18.0	.131 .050	.680 .197	.266 .093	61.5	16.2
18.5	.105 .043	.651 .206	.257 .088	65.4	17.0
19.0	.089 .038	.631 .205	.251 .074	71.6	18.1
19.5	.066 .032	.593 .219	.240 .067	73.5	17.9
20.0	.055 .027	.587 .214	.227 .055	77.4	18.8
20.5	.041 .022	.560 .218	.215 .045	77.5	18.9
21.0	.033 .017	.553 .206	.198 .036	77.1	19.1
21.5	.025 .014	.527 .197	.181 .027	72.5	17.6
22.0	.021 .012	.508 .181	.165 .020	65.5	15.1

AVERAGE IDT SIGNAL PARAMETERS VS. RADIAL IFOV OFFSET

7(11)

RUN#15 TEL.DEFOC=15 R0.DEFOC=100 IFOV=100 Z0=3.5" T0=.989

R [AS]	EO(R) +/-	M1(R) +/-	M2(R) +/-	RMS-D1(R) [MAS]	RMS-D2(R) [MAS]
.0	1.000 .000	.814 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
.5	1.000 .000	.814 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
1.0	1.000 .000	.814 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
1.5	1.000 .000	.814 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
2.0	1.000 .000	.814 .000	.343 .000	.1	.0
2.5	1.000-.001	.815-.001	.343 .000	.1	.0
3.0	.999-.001	.815 .001	.343 .000	.1	.0
3.5	.999 .001	.815-.001	.343 .000	.1	.0
4.0	.999 .001	.815 .000	.343 .000	.2	.0
4.5	.998 .000	.815-.001	.343 .000	.2	.0
5.0	.997 .001	.815 .000	.343 .000	.3	.0
5.5	.997 .001	.816 .000	.343 .000	.4	.0
6.0	.996 .001	.816 .000	.344 .000	.5	.0
6.5	.993 .002	.817 .000	.344 .001	.8	.1
7.0	.991 .003	.817 .002	.344 .001	1.0	.1
7.5	.987 .006	.819 .002	.345 .001	1.5	.2
8.0	.983 .008	.820 .003	.345 .001	1.8	.3
8.5	.974 .012	.822 .004	.346 .001	2.5	.5
9.0	.966 .015	.825 .006	.347 .002	3.1	.6
9.5	.953 .020	.828 .008	.349 .002	4.1	.9
10.0	.938 .025	.831 .010	.350 .003	5.2	1.1
10.5	.921 .028	.835 .012	.352 .004	6.2	1.3
11.0	.893 .031	.839 .014	.355 .006	8.1	1.7
11.5	.869 .036	.843 .019	.357 .009	9.5	2.0
12.0	.834 .037	.847 .023	.359 .012	11.8	2.5
12.5	.798 .036	.849 .030	.361 .017	13.8	3.0
13.0	.755 .036	.851 .038	.363 .022	16.4	3.7
13.5	.712 .036	.851 .046	.364 .028	19.1	4.4
14.0	.663 .033	.850 .058	.364 .035	21.9	5.1
14.5	.610 .034	.847 .068	.363 .041	25.4	6.1
15.0	.560 .038	.842 .084	.360 .050	27.8	6.8
15.5	.506 .038	.835 .093	.356 .056	32.0	8.1
16.0	.449 .044	.823 .114	.350 .066	34.7	8.9
16.5	.398 .049	.811 .124	.342 .071	39.1	10.1
17.0	.346 .052	.795 .143	.333 .080	42.0	11.0
17.5	.299 .053	.778 .153	.322 .083	46.4	12.2
18.0	.252 .057	.755 .169	.309 .089	49.7	13.1
18.5	.212 .055	.726 .183	.301 .089	53.9	14.2
19.0	.183 .053	.699 .183	.293 .081	59.7	15.7
19.5	.146 .051	.656 .205	.286 .080	62.6	16.3
20.0	.124 .047	.640 .202	.270 .069	66.7	17.3
20.5	.099 .043	.602 .213	.258 .061	68.6	17.4
21.0	.083 .039	.589 .208	.240 .052	69.8	17.3
21.5	.065 .036	.559 .208	.223 .044	69.3	16.1
22.0	.055 .034	.540 .202	.207 .038	66.9	14.7

AVERAGE IDT SIGNAL PARAMETERS VS. RADIAL IFOV OFFSET

RUN#16 TEL.DEFOC=15 RO.DEFOC=100 IFOV=110 ZO=3.5" TO=.990

R [CAS]	EO(R) +/-	M1(R) +/-	M2(R) +/-	RMS-D1(R) [MAS]	RMS-D2(R) [MAS]
.0	1.000 .000	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
.5	1.000-.001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
1.0	1.000 .001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
1.5	1.000 .000	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
2.0	1.000 .001	.814-.001	.342 .000	.0	.0
2.5	1.000 .000	.814 .000	.342 .000	.0	.0
3.0	1.000-.001	.814 .000	.342 .000	.1	.0
3.5	.999 .000	.814 .001	.342 .000	.1	.0
4.0	.999 .001	.814 .001	.342 .000	.1	.0
4.5	.999 .000	.814 .001	.342 .000	.1	.0
5.0	.999 .001	.814 .000	.343 .000	.1	.0
5.5	.998 .001	.814-.001	.343 .000	.2	.0
6.0	.998 .001	.815 .000	.343 .000	.2	.0
6.5	.997 .001	.815-.001	.343 .000	.3	.0
7.0	.996 .001	.815 .001	.343 .000	.4	.0
7.5	.994 .002	.816 .001	.343 .000	.6	.1
8.0	.993 .003	.816 .001	.344 .000	.8	.1
8.5	.990 .004	.817 .002	.344 .001	1.1	.1
9.0	.986 .006	.818 .003	.345 .001	1.5	.2
9.5	.980 .009	.820 .003	.345 .001	2.0	.4
10.0	.972 .013	.822 .005	.346 .001	2.6	.5
10.5	.964 .017	.824 .006	.347 .002	3.2	.7
11.0	.948 .021	.828 .008	.349 .002	4.4	.9
11.5	.935 .026	.831 .010	.350 .003	5.3	1.1
12.0	.912 .030	.835 .012	.352 .005	6.9	1.5
12.5	.889 .033	.839 .016	.355 .007	8.3	1.8
13.0	.858 .036	.843 .020	.357 .010	10.2	2.2
13.5	.826 .038	.846 .025	.359 .013	12.3	2.6
14.0	.788 .037	.849 .032	.361 .018	14.5	3.2
14.5	.743 .035	.850 .039	.363 .023	17.4	3.9
15.0	.701 .038	.850 .050	.363 .030	19.5	4.5
15.5	.650 .034	.848 .058	.363 .035	23.0	5.5
16.0	.598 .034	.844 .075	.361 .044	25.5	6.2
16.5	.544 .037	.838 .085	.358 .051	29.4	7.3
17.0	.491 .041	.829 .102	.353 .060	32.2	8.2
17.5	.438 .043	.818 .113	.346 .066	36.1	9.3
18.0	.384 .050	.803 .131	.337 .074	39.3	10.3
18.5	.336 .054	.779 .145	.332 .078	43.2	11.4
19.0	.296 .055	.753 .147	.324 .076	48.2	12.7
19.5	.248 .060	.714 .170	.320 .080	51.4	13.4
20.0	.217 .060	.695 .173	.305 .074	55.2	14.3
20.5	.181 .061	.656 .188	.296 .071	57.7	14.8
21.0	.158 .061	.638 .188	.278 .063	59.5	15.1
21.5	.131 .061	.606 .192	.262 .054	60.7	15.0
22.0	.113 .063	.587 .187	.244 .049	60.7	14.4

AVERAGE IDT SIGNAL PARAMETERS VS. RADIAL IFOV OFFSET

RUN# 17 TEL.DEFOC=15 RO.DEFOC=150 IFOV=90 ZO=5.6" TO=.979

R [AS]	EO(R) +/-	M1(R) +/-	M2(R) +/-	RMS-D1(R) [MAS]	RMS-D2(R) [MAS]
.0	1.000 .000	.818 .000	.345 .000	.0	.0
.5	.999 .000	.819 .000	.345 .000	.3	.0
1.0	.999-.001	.819 .001	.346 .000	.6	.0
1.5	.997 .001	.819 .001	.346 .000	.8	.1
2.0	.995 .002	.820 .002	.346 .001	1.2	.1
2.5	.993 .003	.821 .003	.347 .001	1.5	.2
3.0	.987 .006	.823 .003	.347 .001	2.1	.4
3.5	.984 .008	.824 .005	.348 .001	2.3	.5
4.0	.975 .011	.827 .006	.348 .001	3.0	.7
4.5	.967 .014	.829 .008	.349 .001	3.6	1.0
5.0	.954 .019	.832 .009	.350 .001	4.4	1.3
5.5	.942 .023	.835 .012	.350 .002	5.1	1.5
6.0	.928 .029	.838 .015	.351 .002	5.7	1.6
6.5	.907 .033	.843 .016	.352 .002	7.1	1.9
7.0	.889 .042	.847 .020	.353 .002	7.8	2.0
7.5	.862 .048	.851 .023	.354 .004	9.4	2.2
8.0	.842 .060	.856 .028	.355 .006	10.0	2.2
8.5	.812 .066	.860 .031	.357 .008	11.9	2.5
9.0	.785 .077	.865 .037	.358 .012	13.1	2.7
9.5	.755 .086	.869 .042	.359 .016	14.9	3.0
10.0	.726 .095	.872 .047	.361 .021	16.6	3.5
10.5	.694 .109	.877 .058	.361 .028	17.8	3.9
11.0	.659 .112	.877 .061	.362 .033	20.5	4.7
11.5	.627 .125	.879 .072	.361 .041	21.8	5.3
12.0	.593 .127	.878 .076	.360 .047	24.4	6.2
12.5	.557 .135	.876 .087	.358 .056	26.2	7.0
13.0	.522 .138	.871 .094	.355 .064	28.6	8.0
13.5	.489 .139	.866 .102	.351 .072	30.9	8.9
14.0	.453 .141	.857 .112	.346 .081	33.1	9.8
14.5	.421 .136	.847 .117	.340 .086	36.1	10.9
15.0	.385 .139	.833 .133	.333 .099	37.5	11.3
15.5	.356 .130	.821 .135	.325 .101	41.0	12.3
16.0	.320 .129	.789 .152	.331 .106	44.2	13.2
16.5	.293 .119	.772 .157	.326 .105	48.2	14.1
17.0	.261 .115	.743 .173	.327 .110	50.9	14.5
17.5	.236 .105	.725 .181	.320 .107	54.4	14.9
18.0	.208 .098	.698 .197	.318 .107	57.0	15.0
18.5	.182 .092	.674 .211	.314 .106	59.6	15.0
19.0	.165 .084	.666 .211	.303 .098	62.0	14.9
19.5	.137 .080	.624 .234	.306 .096	63.8	14.3
20.0	.126 .072	.623 .232	.291 .083	65.4	14.2
20.5	.107 .067	.593 .246	.287 .076	66.2	13.9
21.0	.098 .062	.590 .241	.273 .063	66.4	13.7
21.5	.084 .058	.562 .245	.264 .050	66.6	13.4
22.0	.075 .056	.547 .241	.251 .040	65.1	13.1

RUN# 18 TEL.DEFOC=15 RO.DEFOC=150 IFOV=100 Z0=5.6" T0=.985

R [AS]	EO(R) +/-	M1(R) +/-	M2(R) +/-	RMS-D1(R) [MAS]	RMS-D2(R) [MAS]
.0	1.000 .000	.816 .000	.344 .000	.0	.0
.5	.999 .001	.816 .001	.344 .000	.1	.0
1.0	.999 .001	.816 .000	.344 .000	.2	.0
1.5	.999 .001	.816 .000	.344 .000	.3	.0
2.0	.998 .001	.816 .001	.344 .000	.5	.0
2.5	.997 .002	.817 .001	.344 .000	.6	.0
3.0	.994 .003	.817 .001	.345 .001	.9	.1
3.5	.993 .004	.818 .002	.345 .001	1.1	.1
4.0	.989 .006	.819 .003	.345 .001	1.5	.2
4.5	.985 .008	.820 .004	.346 .001	1.8	.3
5.0	.980 .011	.822 .005	.346 .001	2.3	.5
5.5	.974 .014	.824 .006	.347 .001	2.8	.6
6.0	.968 .017	.826 .007	.347 .002	3.2	.8
6.5	.956 .021	.829 .009	.348 .002	4.2	1.1
7.0	.948 .025	.832 .011	.349 .002	4.7	1.3
7.5	.932 .030	.836 .013	.350 .002	5.8	1.6
8.0	.923 .035	.839 .016	.350 .002	6.3	1.7
8.5	.903 .038	.843 .018	.352 .003	7.7	2.0
9.0	.886 .042	.847 .022	.353 .004	8.6	2.1
9.5	.865 .045	.852 .025	.354 .005	9.9	2.2
10.0	.844 .047	.856 .028	.355 .008	11.3	2.4
10.5	.822 .050	.861 .035	.356 .011	12.3	2.6
11.0	.790 .047	.864 .039	.358 .015	14.4	2.9
11.5	.765 .051	.869 .047	.359 .020	15.5	3.3
12.0	.732 .047	.871 .051	.360 .024	17.8	3.8
12.5	.699 .046	.874 .060	.360 .031	19.3	4.4
13.0	.664 .044	.875 .067	.360 .038	21.4	5.1
13.5	.629 .043	.875 .074	.359 .044	23.5	5.9
14.0	.591 .042	.873 .083	.357 .052	25.5	6.8
14.5	.553 .042	.868 .088	.355 .059	28.2	7.8
15.0	.514 .046	.864 .101	.351 .069	29.5	8.5
15.5	.478 .046	.856 .104	.346 .074	32.6	9.7
16.0	.446 .043	.832 .113	.351 .080	35.5	10.7
16.5	.414 .044	.816 .116	.348 .082	38.9	11.8
17.0	.381 .046	.793 .129	.348 .089	41.4	12.5
17.5	.350 .048	.776 .136	.342 .091	44.4	13.2
18.0	.319 .054	.751 .150	.340 .096	46.7	13.5
18.5	.289 .057	.728 .165	.336 .100	49.2	13.9
19.0	.268 .062	.715 .167	.324 .097	51.0	13.8
19.5	.236 .066	.674 .192	.328 .101	52.9	13.6
20.0	.221 .072	.666 .193	.314 .094	54.4	13.3
20.5	.195 .075	.633 .212	.312 .092	55.5	12.7
21.0	.182 .081	.625 .213	.299 .082	56.3	12.0
21.5	.162 .083	.594 .223	.293 .071	57.6	11.0
22.0	.149 .087	.578 .226	.282 .059	57.8	10.2

AVERAGE IDT SIGNAL PARAMETERS VS. RADIAL IFOV OFFSET

RUN# 19 TEL.DEFOC=15 RO.DEFOC=150 IFOV=110 Z0=5.6 T0=.988

R [AS]	ED(R) +/-	M1(R) +/-	M2(R) +/-	RMS-D1(R) [MAS]	RMS-D2(R) [MAS]
.0	1.000 .000	.814 .000	.343 .000	.0	.0
.5	1.000 .000	.814 .000	.343 .000	.1	.0
1.0	1.000 .000	.815 .000	.343 .000	.1	.0
1.5	.999-.001	.815 .000	.343 .000	.1	.0
2.0	.999 .001	.815 .001	.343 .000	.2	.0
2.5	.999 .000	.815 .000	.343 .000	.3	.0
3.0	.998 .000	.815 .001	.343 .000	.4	.0
3.5	.997 .002	.815 .001	.343 .000	.5	.0
4.0	.995 .002	.816 .001	.344 .001	.7	.0
4.5	.994 .004	.817 .002	.344 .001	.9	.1
5.0	.991 .005	.818 .002	.344 .001	1.3	.1
5.5	.988 .007	.819 .003	.345 .001	1.5	.2
6.0	.984 .009	.820 .004	.345 .001	1.8	.3
6.5	.978 .012	.822 .005	.346 .001	2.4	.5
7.0	.973 .015	.823 .006	.346 .002	2.8	.7
7.5	.963 .019	.826 .008	.347 .002	3.6	.9
8.0	.957 .023	.828 .010	.348 .002	4.0	1.1
8.5	.943 .028	.832 .012	.349 .002	5.0	1.4
9.0	.932 .032	.835 .014	.349 .002	5.8	1.6
9.5	.916 .036	.839 .016	.350 .002	6.8	1.8
10.0	.901 .040	.842 .019	.351 .003	7.8	1.9
10.5	.885 .045	.847 .023	.352 .004	8.6	2.0
11.0	.860 .046	.851 .026	.353 .006	10.3	2.3
11.5	.842 .050	.856 .031	.354 .009	11.2	2.4
12.0	.813 .050	.860 .034	.356 .012	13.1	2.7
12.5	.787 .051	.864 .041	.357 .016	14.4	3.0
13.0	.757 .050	.867 .047	.358 .021	16.2	3.4
13.5	.727 .049	.870 .053	.359 .026	17.9	3.9
14.0	.693 .046	.872 .061	.359 .033	19.7	4.6
14.5	.657 .042	.871 .066	.359 .039	22.0	5.4
15.0	.623 .045	.872 .078	.357 .047	23.3	6.0
15.5	.587 .041	.868 .081	.355 .052	25.8	7.1
16.0	.555 .036	.851 .085	.360 .058	28.3	8.0
16.5	.522 .033	.838 .086	.359 .061	31.2	9.1
17.0	.488 .035	.822 .095	.360 .068	33.3	9.9
17.5	.456 .038	.807 .100	.356 .072	35.8	10.7
18.0	.423 .045	.787 .112	.354 .078	37.8	11.2
18.5	.390 .051	.767 .125	.352 .084	40.1	11.7
19.0	.368 .062	.754 .128	.341 .086	41.7	11.9
19.5	.332 .069	.718 .149	.345 .093	43.7	12.0
20.0	.314 .080	.708 .153	.332 .090	45.2	12.1
20.5	.285 .087	.676 .172	.330 .092	46.5	11.9
21.0	.270 .097	.666 .175	.317 .086	47.6	11.7
21.5	.246 .104	.636 .185	.313 .079	49.1	10.9
22.0	.229 .111	.619 .188	.302 .070	49.9	10.3